

LESSONS LEARNED

AGNSW now produce detailed signal flow diagrams—using web-based diagramming tool draw.io—as part of its suite of Conservation documentation for complex works.

Pictured here is *The Rites of When* (2024) by artist Angelica Mesiti. A rich visual and sonic installation commissioned for the Nelson Packer Tank gallery, a former wartime oil bunker beneath the Naala Badu building. The work features seven monolithic vertical screens arranged in a circle within the 2,200-square-metre space.

The corresponding diagram illustrates how the artwork is streamed from two Apple Mac Studios networked together and running QLab. Synchronization is achieved via audio timecode, with Mac Studio 1 acting as the master timecode generator. The timecode signal is sent to the dLive mixer and then returned to both Mac Studios, ensuring precise, synchronized playback across both systems.

The dLive mixer also receives the audio from Mac Studio 1, routing Dante audio via the switch to Meyer speakers and subwoofer. Video outputs pass through 4K60 emulators to HDMI transmitters and receivers, driving seven projectors displaying visuals on microperforated screens. Audio travels over Dante to AVIO interfaces connected to Meyer box speakers embedded in the screens.

The intricate systems behind *GROUNDLOOP* and *The Rites of When* demonstrate that preserving media artworks is as much about understanding infrastructure as it is about safeguarding the artist's Master files.

Customised documentation—like signal flow diagrams, network maps, and codec specifications—is vital for installation, troubleshooting, and upholding the artist's vision. By capturing these details with precision, we ensure that time-based artworks can be authentically re-experienced far into the future.

Above: 'The Rites of When' signal flow diagram by Daniel Kilp.
Left: Installation view of Angelica Mesiti 'The Rites of When', 2024, 7-channel digital video installation, colour, sound, approx 30 min, collection of the artist, commissioned by the Art Gallery of New South Wales for the Nelson Packer Tank, 2024 © Angelica Mesiti, photo © Art Gallery of New South Wales, Jenni Carter